

The Influence of Compensation, Competency, and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Work Engagement as a Moderating Variable at DPRKPP of Surabaya

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine and analyze the effect of compensation (X1), Competence (X2), Work Environment (X3) and The Work Engagement (Z) on Employee performance (Y) of honorary employees at The Surabaya Public Housing, Settlement Area, and Land Services Office in 2023. The research population was 202 honorary employees of The Surabaya Public Housing, Settlement Area, and Land Services Office in 2023. This study uses a quantitative approach to analyze variables. This study uses primary data collected by distributing questionnaires. Based on the Slovin formula, a sample of 135 people was taken with a sampling technique using simple random sampling. The data analysis technique uses Partial Least Square with SmartPLS 3.0. The research results show that compensation has an effect on employee performance. Competency has an effect on employee performance. The work environment has an effect on employee performance. The work engagement has an effect on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: compensation, competency, work environment, work engagement, employee performance

INTRODUCTION

Knowing the performance of employees in an agency is a very important step in maintaining and improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization. Information about employee performance can assist agencies in identifying areas where efficiency can be improved. This means that organizational resources, such as time and budget, can be better allocated to achieving organizational goals.

Public people have high expectations for public sector organizations such as DPRKPP Surabaya. Organizations can ensure that the services provided to society are of high quality and meet their needs by knowing the performance of employees. Organizations can build a positive reputation and increase public trust towards the services provided by demonstrating good employee performance.

The direct effect of employee performance can be felt on the effectiveness and efficiency of services provided by the Surabaya DPRKPP Office. When employees work well, development projects can be completed according to a predetermined schedule and budget, existing infrastructure can be maintained properly, and the community can get adequate services.

Fair and adequate compensation is an important element in motivating employees. When employees feel that they are being properly rewarded for their contributions and hard work, they tend to be more motivated and satisfied with their work. Employees who feel valued and rewarded for their contributions and efforts are more motivated to achieve targets and perform better. Competitive compensation can help companies retain their top talent, reduce *turnover* rates, and save on hiring and retraining costs.

Employees who have knowledge, skills, and abilities that match their duties and responsibilities tend to be more effective and efficient in carrying out their jobs. Employees who have competencies that match their duties have the knowledge and skills necessary to complete tasks well. **They** more easily adjust to changes in tasks or work environments. They are better able to learn new things and adapt quickly.

Competent employees can cope better with tasks and face challenges with more confidence. They can avoid mistakes and problems that can arise, improve employee retention, reduce turnover rates, and have the required skills that can help the company to continue to grow and innovate.

A conducive work environment creates an atmosphere that supports productivity and creativity. This includes physical aspects such as adequate facilities and equipment, as well as social aspects such as relationships between employees and relationships with superiors. A positive environment can encourage employees to collaborate, innovate, and feel comfortable in carrying out their duties.

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Employees need adequate facilities and equipment to carry out their jobs efficiently, this includes access to the latest technology, good work equipment, and appropriate infrastructure. In addition, good relationships between employees and good relationships between employees and superiors create a positive work atmosphere, effective communication, and collaboration in the team.

Honorary employees generally work with contract status or employment agreements that are temporary or non-permanent. This creates uncertainty in their careers, including the risk of losing their jobs every time the contract expires. This uncertainty can interfere with work focus and motivation, as honorary employees often feel they have no long-term job security.

Based on the compensation received, honorary employee benefits are often lower than those of civil servants. This can lead to financial dissatisfaction that can affect their performance. In addition, the lack of benefits can also hinder honorary employees' ability to meet their basic needs, such as children's education or health care.

Honorary employees often do not get the same facilities as civil servants, such as access to training and development, adequate health insurance, paid leave, or pension funds. This inequality can reduce the well-being of honorary employees and can also hinder their motivation to do a good job. Honorary employees have limited access to the training and professional development needed to improve their qualifications, unlike those obtained by ASN employees. This can be an obstacle in the improvement of their competence and performance in the workplace.

Based on the background of these problems, this study aims to analyze the effect of compensation, competence, and work environment on employee performance in honorary employees at the Surabaya DPRKPP Office, by considering work attachment as a moderation variable.

THEORETICAL STUDIES

The definition of compensation according to Sutrisno (2020: 187) is all types of awards in the form of money or not money given to employees properly and fairly for their services in achieving company goals.

Enny (2019: 37) defines compensation as a form of compensation given to employees as a form of appreciation for their contributions and work to the company. Meanwhile, according to Sastrohadwiryo and Syuhada (2019: 224), compensation is a reward for services or remuneration provided by the company to the workforce, because the workforce contributes energy and thoughts for the progress of the company to achieve the goals that have been set, both in the short and long term.

Compensation according to Ansory and Indrasari (2018: 231) is a reward for services which is given regularly and in a certain amount by the company to employees for the contribution of their energy that has been given to achieve company goals in the form of wages and salaries.

Sutrisno (2020: 191) suggests that there are several factors that are taken into consideration for the provision of compensation, namely the level of living costs, the level of compensation applicable in other companies, the level of company ability, the type of work and the size of responsibility, applicable laws and regulations and the role of trade unions.

According to Silaen, *et al* (2021: 100), compensation given to employees consists of two types. First, financial compensation is compensation received by employees in the form of money or monetary value, either periodically (weekly, monthly, or yearly) such as salaries or wages, bonuses, benefits, insurance, and others paid by organizations or companies. Second, compensation that is non-financial, namely compensation provided by organizations or companies especially with the intention of retaining employees in the long term. What is included in non-financial compensation is the implementation of service programs for employees who strive to create pleasant working conditions and environments, such as tourism programs, provision of canteen or cafeteria facilities, provision of places of worship at work, and so on.

The definition of competence according to Sudaryo *et al.*, (2018: 184) is the level of a person's ability to carry out their authority and responsibility in carrying out their duties effectively and efficiently.

Competence according to Nuryadin, *et al* (2019: 117) is a permanent individual characteristic or personality that can affect a person's performance. Competence according to Enny (2019:30) is everything that a person has in the form of knowledge, skills, and other internal factors of individuals to be able to do a job based on the knowledge and skills possessed. Meanwhile, according to Dewi and Harjojo (2019: 153), competence is a part of personality that is deep and inherent to a person and predictable behavior in various circumstances and job tasks.

The benefits of competence and its use in human resource management according to Dewi and Harjojo (2019: 158) are, Clarify work standards and expectations to be achieved, Employee selection tools, Maximize productivity, Basic for the development of a remuneration system, Facilitate adaptation to change, and Align work behavior with organizational values

The aspect contained in the concept of Competency according to Gordon in Sutrisno (2020: 204) is Knowledge (*knowledge*), Understanding, Ability, Value, *Attitude*, and Interest.

Sedarmayanti in Silaen, *et al.* (2021: 199) states that the work environment is the entire tool and material faced, the surrounding environment where a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements, both as individuals and as a group and is one of the factors that affect the performance of a worker.

Work environment according to Mardiana in Sudaryo, *et al.* (2018:47) is an environment where employees do their daily work.

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Good working environment conditions will make employees feel comfortable at work.

The work environment according to Enny (2019: 56) is everything around employees that can affect employee job satisfaction in carrying out their work, so that maximum work results will be obtained where in the work environment there are work facilities that support employees in completing the tasks assigned to them.

Work environment according to Silaen, *et al.* (2021:200) consists of 2 (two) types, First, the physical work environment, is the environment around a worker's workplace that can affect workers either directly or indirectly. This physical work environment is closely related to the facilities and infrastructure owned by a worker in his work environment. The physical work environment consists of Coloring, Hygiene, Air circulation or exchange, Lighting or lighting, Security, Noise level. Second, the non-physical work environment, is all the circumstances that occur related to work relationships, such as superior and subordinate relationships and work relationships with fellow colleagues Employee performance according to Nuryadin *et al.* (2019:35) is a work achievement Employees, either individually or in groups carried out in accordance with the duties and responsibilities given based on the quality or quantity of work produced. While employee performance according to Silaen *et al.* (2021: 2) is defined as a person's work performance based on mutually agreed quality and quantity. According to Syaifuddin (2018: 1) performance is basically the responsibility of every individual working in the organization.

Soedjono in Syaifuddin (2018: 70) mentioned 7 (seven) criteria that can be used to measure individual employee performance, namely Quality, Quantity, Punctuality, Effectiveness, Independence, Work Commitment, and Responsibility.

Work attachment according to Sari *et al.* (2021:13) describes the close relationship between individuals and their work. Strong relationships are characterized by high enthusiasm in performing tasks, emotional involvement in carrying out work, and enjoying every task performed.

Employee attachment according to Agustini (2019: 140) is an affectionate and cognitive aspect as well as the physical aspect of employees to the company where the employee voluntarily provides results

or maximum work performance in achieving company goals. Employee work attachment can also result in increased financial productivity and play a positive role in correcting less productive employee behavior such as truancy and the desire to leave work or the workplace (Adi and Fitriana, 2018: 2). According to Schaufeli and Baker in Agustini (2019:146), there are 3 (three) indicators or characteristics of employee engagement. First, *Vigor*, is a state full of high energy levels and mentally tough in doing work such as having high energy, having mental toughness, giving the best effort.

Second, *Dedication*, is a significant feeling of work, attentiveness, and interest in doing work such as high enthusiasm, inspiration, feeling proud, and liking challenges.

Third, *Absorbion* is a description of the behavior of employees who give full attention to work and are involved in a job such as concentrating fully, happy to be involved in work, and feeling that time is running fast when working.

Based on theoretical foundations and some previous research, the conceptual framework in this study can be described as follows:

Figure 1.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the research framework, the following hypothesis was submitted:

H1: Compensation influences employee performance at DPRKPP Surabaya.

H2: Competency influences employee performance at DPRKPP Surabaya.

H3: The work environment influences the performance of employees at DPRKPP Surabaya.

H4: Work attachment influences employee performance at DPRKPP Surabaya.

H5: Employment attachment moderates the influence of compensation on employee performance at DPRKPP Surabaya.

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H6: Work attachment moderates the influence of competence on employee performance at DPRKPP Surabaya.

H7: Work attachment moderates the influence of the work environment on employee performance at DPRKPP Surabaya.

RESEARCH METHODS

The population in this study is honorary employees who work in the Public Housing and Settlement and Land Office (DPRKPP) of Surabaya City, based on the criteria determined by the researcher, the population members are 202 managers, while the respondents used as a sample use the formula proposed by Slvin, namely,

$$S = \frac{N}{N \cdot d^2 + 1}$$

With an accuracy level of accuracy (D) 5%, so that the respondents who were further processed amounted to 135 managers. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents. The questionnaire consists of 5 variables, namely:

1) Compensation Variable with 7 question items, 2) Leadership Variable with 6 items, 3) Motivation Variable with 8 items, and 4) Employee Performance Variables totaling 7 items, 5) Work Attachment Variables totaling 11 items. Each of these items uses a lickert scale with an answer range of 1 to 5.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis technique used in this study is *Partial Least Square* (PLS) and the data was processed using *SmartPLS* software. Based on the results of the test output above, the loading factor obtained from each relationship between indicators and their constructs has varying values and it can be said that the indicator value is above 0.70 so that all indicators are valid and there are no values that show below 0.70. The next stage is the second check is by looking at the value of Composite Reliability and Cronbachs Alpha.

From the value of composite reliability for all exogenous constructs, endogenous is all very reliable because the value is above 0.70 so it can be said that Compensation (X1), Competence (X2), Work Environment (X3), Employee Performance (Y), and Work Attachment (Z) have good validity and reliability.

Based on the cronbachs alpha values for all exogenous constructs, endogenous are all very reliable because the value is above 0.70, it can be concluded that Compensation (X1), Competency (X2), Work Environment (X3), Employee Performance (Y), and Work Attachment (Z) have good validity and reliability.

Hypothesis testing in this study using the Bootstrap technique aims to predict causal relationships between variables or hypothesis testing by showing the level of significance. In SmartPLS, the outer model score indicated by the P Values sinificance value should be less than the 5 percent alpha value (0.05).

Table 1. Output Path Coefficients

Relationship	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
X1 >Y	0,468	6,838	0,000	Significant
X2 >Y	0,161	4,329	0,000	Significant
X3 >Y	0,195	6,300	0,000	Significant
With >Y	0,201	3,219	0,001	Significant
X1*Z>Y	0,140	2,501	0,013	Significant
X2*Z>Y	-0,124	2,718	0,007	Significant
X3*Z>Y	-0,014	0,461	0,645	Insignificant

Source: SmartPLS Processed Data, 2023 X1: Compensation

X2 : Competency

X3 : Work Environment

Y : Employee Performance

Z : Work Attachment

Hypothesis testing is carried out by comparing the value of t-statistics on each latent variable with t-tables (1.96), that is, it is said to be significant if the statistical latent variable is greater than 1.96. After conducting research and analyzing the data obtained from respondents to test the hypothesis, the results of the study can be described as follows:

1. The results of the analysis show a significant effect of compensation on employee performance, this is shown by the results of statistical testing which shows that compensation has a significant positive influence on employee performance at a significance level of 5% (p = 0.000). These findings strongly support the hypothesis proposed that compensation has an effect on employee performance. This shows that the better the compensation system applied, the higher the performance of employees in DPRKPP

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Surabaya. Compensation (X1) affects Employee Performance (Y), because the $t > t_{table}$ is $6,838 > 1,979$.

2. The results of the analysis show a significant influence of competence on employee performance, this is shown by the results of statistical testing which shows that competence has a significant positive influence on employee performance at a significance level of 5% ($p = 0.000$). This finding supports the hypothesis proposed (H2), which states that competence affects employee performance in the Surabaya DPRKPP. Competency (X2) affects Employee Performance (Y), because the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $4.329 > 1,979$.

3. The results of the analysis show a significant influence of the work environment on employee performance at the Public Housing and Settlement and Land Office (DPRKPP) Surabaya, this is supported by the results of research that shows a positive and significant influence between work environment variables on employee performance at a confidence level of 5% (0.000). Work Environment (X3) effect on Employee Performance (Y), because the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $6,300 > 1,979$.

4. The results showed that the variable of work attachment had a significant positive influence on employee performance at a significance level of 5% (0.001), this is strong evidence that supports the hypothesis proposed. This indicates that there is a real and positive relationship between the level of work engagement and employee performance at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Area Office (DPRKPP). Work Attachment (Z) affects Employee Performance (Y), because the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $3.219 > 1.979$.

5. Based on the results of the study, it is known that work attachment moderates the effect of compensation on employee performance with a significance value at 5% (0.013). This means that it shows the effect of the interaction between the variables of work attachment and compensation on employee performance. In general, this result indicates that the effect of compensation on employee performance at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Office (DPRKPP) is not only influenced by the compensation itself, but also by the level of work attachment felt by employees. The Moderating Construct of Work Attachment (Z) moderates the effect of Compensation (X1) on Employee Performance (Y), because the $t > t_{table}$ is $2.501 > 1.979$.

6. Based on the results of the study, it is known that work attachment moderates the influence of competence on employee performance in a negative direction with a significance value at 5% (0.007). This means that it shows the influence of interaction between work attachment variables that weaken the influence of competence on employee performance. That is, the level of work attachment that High can reduce the positive impact of competence on employee performance. The Moderating Construct of Work Attachment (Z) moderates the effect of Competency (X2) on Employee Performance (Y), because the $t > t_{table}$ is $2,718 > 1,979$.

7. Based on the results of the study, it is known that work attachment does not moderate the influence of the work environment on employee performance with a significance value at 5% (0.645). This means that it shows the absence of interaction influence between work attachment variables that reinforce the influence of the work environment on employee performance. That is, the level of work attachment cannot add to the positive impact of the work environment on employee performance. The Moderating Construct of Work Attachment (Z) moderates the effect of the Work Environment (X3) on Employee Performance (Y), because the $t < t_{table}$ is $0.461 < 1.979$.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, the conclusions in this study are as follows:

1. Compensation affects the performance of employees at the Public Housing Office
2. Competence affects the performance of employees at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Area Office (DPRKPP).
3. The work environment affects the performance of employees at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Area Office (DPRKPP).
4. Work attachment affects the performance of employees at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Area Office (DPRKPP).
5. Work attachment moderates the effect of compensation on employee performance at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Office (DPRKPP).
6. Work engagement moderates in a negative direction on the influence of competence on employee performance at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Office (DPRKPP) in a negative direction.
7. Work attachment does not moderate the influence of the work environment on employee performance at the Surabaya Public Housing and Settlement and Land Area Office (DPRKPP).

REFERENCES

- 1) Adi, A. N dan N. F. Fitriana. 2018. *Employee Engagement (Pada Sektor Bisnis Dan Publik)*. Malang: IRDH (Research & Publishing).
- 2) Agustini, Fauzia. 2019. *Strategi Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Medan:UISU Press
- 3) Anggraini, A., H. Tridayanti., dan E. Damayanti. 2021. The Influence of Work Environment and Perceived Organizational

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- Support on the Employee Performance of PT Y in Surabaya with Employee Engagement as an Intervening and Settlement and Land Area Services Office (DPRKPP) of Surabaya. Variable. *Jurnal Ekonomi*. 21(1): 35-51.
- 4) Anshory, A dan M. Indrasari. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Sidoarjo: Indomedia Pustaka.
 - 5) Ardiansyah, F dan B. Budiono. 2022. Pengaruh Kompensasi Terhadap Employee Engagement Dan Dampaknya Pada Employee Performance. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*. 10(1): 110-122.
 - 6) Ayu, N., N. Gani., dan W. Abdullah. 2022. Pengaruh Kompetensi Sumber Daya Manusia, Lingkungan Kerja, Dan Kompensasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dengan Motivasi Kerja Sebagai Variabel Moderasi Pada Bank BTN KCS Makasar. *IBEF (Islamic Banking, Economy & Financial Journal)*. 3(1): 24-42.
 - 7) Budiprasetya, A dan S. Johannes Lo. 2020. Mediation Acts from Employee Engagement Which Affects the Employee Competencies and Innovative Work Behaviour on Employee Performance at PT Tetra Pak Indonesia. *Dinasti International Journal of Management Science*. 1(6): 680-688.
 - 8) Dewi, D. P dan Harjojo. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Tangerang: Unpam Press.
 - 9) Efendi, S dan A. Yusuf. 2021. Influence Of Competence, Compensation And Motivation On Employee Performance With Job Satisfaction As Intervening Variable In The Environment Of Indonesian Professional Certification Authority. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*. 5(3): 1078- 1088.
 - 10) Enny, Mahmudah. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Surabaya: Ubhara Manajemen Press.
 - 11) Fatyandri, A. N dan W. Yang. 2023. Analisis Pengaruh dari Keterikatan Kerja Karyawan, Lingkungan Kerja, Motivasi Kerja dan Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan terhadap Kinerja Karyawan dengan Mediasi Komitmen Organisasi pada Perusahaan Manufaktur Batam. *Jurnal Bahana Manajemen Pendidikan*. 12(1): 41-52.
 - 12) Ghozali, Imam. 2018. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS 21 Update PLS Regresi*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
 - 13) Hardani., N. H. Auliya., H. Andriani., R. A. Fardani., J. Ustiawaty, E. F. Utami., D. J. Sukmana., dan R. R. Istiqomah. 2020. *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif & Kuantitatif*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Ilmu.
 - 14) Haryadi, A dan P. Wahyuni. 2022. Analysis of Employee Engagement as A Variable to Mediate The Influence of Competence and Work Environment on Employee Performance in The Yogyakarta Special Region Transportation Office. *Journal of Community Development in Asia (JCDA)*. 5(2): 42-53.
 - 15) Kristanto, A. D dan E. Tajib. 2023. Pengaruh Compensation Dan Job Satisfaction Terhadap Employee Performance Dimediasi Employee Engagement Pada Bank Swasta Di Jakarta. *Glosains Jurnal Sains Global Indonesia*. 4(1): 9-21.
 - 16) Mukminin, A., A. Habibi., L. D. Prasojo., dan L. Yuliana. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Dalam Pendidikan*. Yogyakarta: UNY Press.
 - 17) Nadeak, Bernadetha. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Pendidikan Era Industri 4.0*. Jakarta: UKI Press.
 - 18) Natakusumah, M. O., S. Hidayatullah., I. Windhyastiti., dan P. Sudibyo. 2022. Pengaruh Work-Life Balance, Lingkungan Kerja Dan Keterikatan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Coffeeshop Di Perumahan Kota Wisata Cibubur, Kabupaten Bogor. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen (JIMMU)*. 7(1): 133-143.
 - 19) Novita, E. I., Y. Cahya F., Dan P. Meilani. 2023. Job Motivation And Work Environment Effects On Employee Performance With Employee Engagement As A Mediating Variable At The Ministry Of Foreign Affairs Of The Republic Of Indonesia. *Enrichment: Journal of Management*. 13(4): 2605-2614.
 - 20) Nuryadin, D., Tohirin, dan Ilhamdi. 2019. *Perilaku Organisasi Modern*. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media
 - 21) Pashiera, R. S dan Budiono. 2023. Peran Work Engagement Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Pengaruh Psychological Well-Being Dan Work Environment Terhadap Employee Performance. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen (JIM)*. 11(2): 393-405.
 - 22) Pitaloka, E dan F. M. Putri. 2021. The Impact Of Employee Engagement And Organizational Commitment On Employee Performance. *Business Management Journal*. 17(2): 117-133.
 - 23) Rembulan, G. D., H. Limei., dan F. Nurprihatin. 2021. The Effect of Work Environment, Motivation, and Leadership on Employee Performance with Employee Engagement as Mediating Variable. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Systems*. 14(2): 180-190.
 - 24) Renaldy, Aldy. 2021. Pengaruh Employee Engagement, Budaya Organisasi, Dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Divisi Line Maintenance PT. Batam Aero Teknik Jakarta. *JIMEN (Jurnal Inovatif Mahasiswa Manajemen)*. 1(2): 103-112.
 - 25) Saengchai, S., P. Siriattakul., dan K. Jermisittiparsert. 2019. The Mediating Role of Employee Engagement between Team and Co-worker Relation, Work Environment, Training and Development and Employee Performance. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*. 23(4): 853- 865.
 - 26) Salsabila N. S dan S. Johannes Lo. 2023. The Influences of Competency and Compensation on Employee Performance at PT Balai Pustaka (Persero) as Mediated by Work Engagement. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*. 8(2): 169-174.

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- 27) Santoso, H., N. Mas., dan M. Mas'ud. 2022. Pengaruh Employee Engagement Dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Melalui Good Governance Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Pegawai Kantor Kecamatan Prigen Kabupaten Pasuruan). *Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar Dan Sosial Humaniora*. 1(12): 2471- 2490.
- 28) Sari, E. Y. D., K. Bashori., dan Purwadi. 2021. *Keterikatan Kerja dan Peran Aspek Psikologi Positif*. Yogyakarta: UAD Press.
- 29) Sarinah, L dan I. Rachmayanty. 2021. Keterikatan Kerja (Work Engagement) Mampu Meningkatkan Kinerja Karyawan PT. BPRS Patriot Bekasi. *Jurnal Ilmiah MEA (Manajemen, Ekonomi, dan Akuntansi)*. 5(3): 2543- 2557.
- 30) Sastrohadiwiryo, S dan A. H. Syuhada. 2019. *Manajemen Tenaga Kerja Indonesia Pendekatan Administratif dan Operasional*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- 31) Setyawati, H. Abrilia., G. Wiwoho., B. W. Adi., A. Hidayat., dan O. F. Hilabi. 2023. *Journal of International Conference Proceedings (JICP)*.6(1): 182-191.
- 32) Silaen, N. R., Syamsuriansyah., R. Chairunnisah., M. R. Sari., E. Mahriani., R. Tanjung., D. Triwardhani., A. Haerany., A. Masyuroh., D. G. Satriawan., A. S. Lestari., O. Arifudin., Z. Rialmi., dan S. Putra. 2021. *Kinerja Karyawan*. Bandung: Widina Bhakti Persada.
- 33) Sudaryo, Y., A. Ariwibowo., dan N. A. Sofiati. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Kompensasi Tidak Langsung, Dan Lingkungan Kerja Fisik*. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- 34) Sugiyono. 2018. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif Dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 35) Sumiati dan N. Hasan. 2018. Effect of Compensation, Communication and Spirituality at Work on the Performance of the Turnover Intention as an Intervening Variable. *International Symposium Proceeding*. Hal: 34-39.
- 36) Suryani, N. K dan J. Foeh. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Tinjauan Praktis Aplikatif*. Bali: Nilacakra.
- 37) Susila, Muktar Redy. 2023. The Role Of Work Engagement In Mediating The Effect Of Job Characteristics And Compensation On Performance. *Asian Management and Business Review*. 3(1): 60-73.
- 38) Sutrisno, Edy. 2020. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Kencana.
- 39) Syahputra, Erwin. 2021. Keterikatan Karyawan Dan Kompetensi Dalam Mempengaruhi Kinerja KaryawanPT. Gramedia Asri Media Kediri. *Journal Of Academic And Multidicipline Research*. 1(1): 136 –141.
- 40) Syaifuddin. 2018. *Motivasi Dan Kinerja Pegawai Pendekatan Riset*. Sidoarjo: Indomedia Pustaka.
- 41) Trisninawati dan E. Elpanso. 2021. Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Lingkungan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Outsourcing Di Mediasi Employee Engagement. *Journal Management, Business, and Accounting*. 20(3): 275-284.
- 42) Widodo, E., Ujianto., dan S. Riyadi. 2020. The Influence Of Competence, Locus Of Control, Self-Concept, Career Clarity, And Work Climate On Job Satisfaction And Employee Performance Of Ditlantas Regional Police And Satlantas Resort Police In East Java. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*. 22(11): 55-62.
- 43) Yang, Y dan Y. C. Chang. 2023. A Study On The Relationship Between Teacher Competency And Job Performance Under Human Resource Management In Higher Education. *Educational Research and Reviews*. 18(8): 203-217.